
E-Government Policy Models in Handling Poverty Problems in The Hopeful Family Program (Case Study: Bandung Regency West.)

Disson Muhammad Fauzi¹, Budiharjo², Diana Nur Fatimah³, Bambang Sudaryana⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Public Administration Programe, Dr. Moestopo Beragama University Jakarta

ABSTRACT: This study aims to describe the implementation of e-government with explains the quality of information on the West Bandung Regency Government website. The quality of information on e-government websites has an important role because it will have a broad impact on society. Information submitted by official government channels will be considered valid by the public, so that if the information submitted is incorrect it will result in reduced public trust in the government.

Based on the results of observations on website content, the implementation of e-government in West Bandung Regency can be categorized in the presence (informative) stage towards the interactive stage. As stated by Baum & Maio (2000), this stage indicates that the Bendung Barat website is still limited to providing static information, and has not provided space for the public to interact online with government elements.

The results of this study conclude that in general the quality of information on the West Bandung Regency Government website is quite good. Weaknesses that can reduce the value of the quality of information exist in the dimensions of the completeness of the information, namely the existence of several links that lead to blank pages. The recommendation given from the results of this study is to increase improvement efforts so that all menus and links contained on the website can be completed with relevant information, so that users can obtain complete and accurate information.

This study describes empirical phenomena related to the quality of information using 5 (five) dimensions of measurement. For researchers who wish to continue this research, they can expand the area of study by measuring using a wider dimension of information quality

KEYWORDS: Information quality, Website, government, communication technology

INTRODUCTION

Based on the problem background, problem identification, and problem limitation, the problems in this study are formulated as follows:

1. What is the relationship between each variable of the E-Government Model Policy, poverty alleviation, and the family hope program, and the implications for Good Government Governance in West Bandung Regency?
2. How big is the influence of the E-Government Model Policy on the Family Hope Program in West Bandung Regency?
3. How big is the influence of the Handling of Poverty Problems on the Family Hope Program in West Bnadung Regency?
4. How big is the influence of the Family Hope Program on Good Government Governance in West Bandung Regency?
5. How big is the influence of the E-Government Model Policy, poverty alleviation and the Family Hope Program directly on Good Government Governance in West Bandung Regency?
6. How big is the influence of the E-Government Model Policy, poverty alleviation and the Family Hope Program on Good Government Governance, both partially and simultaneously in West Bandung Regency?

Plans and problem solving ideas are carried out so that they are effective, the stages are (1) identify the problem. In this stage, it is very important for researchers to see the problem from various perspectives; (2), problem analysis, to be effective Required skills that need to be used to analyze problems are collecting data, analyzing data, finding facts and analyzing constricting factors before problems occur. (3), Brainstorming, After finding the cause of the problem, then brainstorming to find possible solutions by collaborating with the Team with the stages: creative thinking, prediction, making possibilities, designing projects, and planning projects; (4) Make decisions, and (5) Take Action

1. PKH adheres to the Regulation of the Minister of Social Affairs Number 1 of 2018
2. Decree of the Minister of Administrative Reform No. 63 of 2003 which outlines general guidelines for the administration of public services.

E-Government Policy Models in Handling Poverty Problems in The Hopeful Family Program (Case Study: Bandung Regency West.)

3. In accordance with the Instruction of the President of the Republic of Indonesia No. 03 of 2003 concerning National policies and strategies for e-government development and the decision of the Minister for Administrative Reform No. 13/Kep/M,PAN/1/2003 concerning general guidelines for internet electronic offices in industrial environments Government and Law No. 11 of 2008 concerning Information and Electronic Transactions, and Law No. 14 of 2008 concerning Public Information Disclosure

The theoretical basis that uses appropriate research variables is as follows: E-Government, which is the most common e-Government application, namely where the government builds and implements various information technology portfolios with the main objective of improving interaction relations with the community (the people). In other words, the main goal of developing a G-to-C type e-Government application is to bring the government closer to its people through various access channels so that people can easily reach their government to fulfill various daily service needs.

Poverty Alleviation; Poverty is a major problem that must be solved. Synergistic and systematic poverty alleviation must be carried out so that all citizens are able to enjoy a dignified life. Therefore, the synergy of all stakeholders is needed.

Poverty is a reflection of the social and economic entities of the majority of the population in rural areas which are closely related to inequality which is largely due to the workings of the capitalist system which has co-opted Indonesian rural areas since colonialism (Elizabeth, 2007). The causes of poverty can be grouped into four parts, namely: (1) facilities and infrastructure (2) natural resources and technology (3) human resources, and (4) institutions and organizations. Poverty can be categorized into absolute, relative, poverty prone or due to geography (poverty in urban and rural areas).

There are many opinions regarding good governance, one of which according to Mardiasmo (2019:17) is: according to the World Bank it defines good governance as: "The way statement is used in managing economic and social resources for the development of society". Meaning: "emphasizes the way the government manages social and economic resources for the benefit of community development." Meanwhile, the United Nation Development Program (UNDP) defines governance as: "the exercise of political, economic, and administrative authority to manage a nation's affairs at all levels. Meaning: "emphasizing the political, economic and administrative aspects of state management".

And then according to Mardiasmo, (2019:17). The World Bank places more emphasis on how the government manages social and economic resources for the benefit of community development, while the UNDP places more emphasis on the political, economic and administrative aspects of managing the country. Political governance refers to the policy/strategy formulation process. Economic governance refers to the decision-making process in the economic field which has implications for issues of equity, reducing poverty, and improving the quality of life. Administrative governance refers to the policy implementation system

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Website Overview The West Bandung Regency Government

The content on the West Bandung Regency main website is static and general in nature, such as government structures, work units, permits, tourist objects, census data, and so on. The information contained in it contains a compilation of data from various SKPDs as well as static information which is usually updated on a semester or yearly basis. The front page of the website has several menus, namely Information, Agenda, News, Downloads, Photo galleries, Contacts, SIM, and Investment opportunities. Apart from accessing through the menu, several links are also available directly on the website page to download various articles, polls regarding the quality of the website, headlines of some regional news, as well as links to a number of Regional Work Unit (SKPD) websites.

The second website that became the research sample is the West Bandung Regency Government Public Relations website which is managed by the Public Relations Section which is under the Regional Secretariat of the West Bandung Regency Government. This website can be accessed via the address humas.bengkaliskab.go.id. News regarding the official activities of the Regent, Deputy Regent, or Regional Secretary is the focus of the information on the Public Relations website. The news was written and sent directly by the staff of the Public Relations Section of the West Bandung Regency Government who were specifically assigned as news coverage during the event. The Head of the Coverage Section for the Public Relations Section explained in the interview that apart from being displayed on the Public Relations website, the news was also published in several local daily newspapers in West Bandung Regency. That way, the wider community can find out about the activities of regional leaders and events in their area.

The third website to be sampled is the Bengkalis Regency Communications and Informatics Transportation Agency (Dishubkominfo), which can be accessed at the address Dishubkominfo.bengkaliskab.go.id. This website is managed independently by the Department of Transportation, Communication and Informatics, Bengkalis Regency. In general, the scope of work of the Dishubkominfo is divided into two fields, namely transportation and telecommunications.

Based on the formulation of its vision and mission, the Dishubkominfo Bengkalis Regency has the duties and functions of ensuring the safety and smooth running of land, sea and air transportation by creating transportation, communication and informatics facilities and infrastructure that are appropriate and on target in order to increase development and regional revenues in order to create a community prosperous. Menus that can be accessed on this website include: Profile, Legal Products, Licensing, IP Camera, Photo Gallery, Contact Us, and Transportation.

E-Government Policy Models in Handling Poverty Problems in The Hopeful Family Program (Case Study: Bandung Regency West.)

The fourth website which is the research sample is the website of the Integrated Investment and Licensing Services Agency (BPMP2T) which can be accessed at the address bpmp2t.bengkaliskab.go.id. BPMP2T West Bandung Regency is a work unit that has the task and function of promoting the potential of West Bandung Regency and providing investment information to the public. Besides that, BPMP2T also implements the concept of one-door licensing to make it easier for the public to take care of various permits. Menus that can be accessed on the BPMP2T website include Profiles, Investment Opportunities, Licensing Services, Legal Products, News, Photo Galleries, Agenda and Contacts.

The results of the analysis are depicted in Figure 1. To provide a complete picture, the researchers compared the four dimensions of service quality with the criteria for the basic form of local government websites based on guidelines from the ministry of communication and information in the following table:

Table

Comparison of the Dimensions of E-government Service Quality with the Criteria for the Basic Shape of Local Government Websites

E-government Service Quality Dimensions (Papadomichelaki & Mentzas, 2011)	Government Website Basic Shape Criteria Area (Kemenkominfo, 2003)
Efficiency	
1. Clarity and ease for following the website structure	-
2. The effectiveness of the search menu (engine searcher) on the web	-
3. Web organizing quality	Functionality, accessibility and convenience (local government website design is professional, interesting and useful)
4. Suitability of the website with the needs of service users	Functions, accessibility and convenience (oriented to the needs of the community, providing information and services that are wanted by society)
5. Details of the information provided	-
6. Information freshness	Effective content (users have the right to expect content from a website government data is valid, recent and appropriate)
7. Information to fill out the form	-
Trust	
Security in getting users name and password	-
2. Amount of personal data required – for authentication on the website	-
3. Secure data archiving	-
4. Utilization of service user data in accordance with the initial purpose of data input	-
Reliability	
1. Speed of downloading forms from the site	-
2. Availability and ease of access whenever needed	-
3. The certainty of success in getting the service in one try	-
4. Timeliness of preparation service	-
5. Website page speed opened/ downloaded	-
6. Optimal site functionality with any browser	Function, accessibility and convenience (Anti-discrimination for users, in which the website can be accessed regardless of the computer facilities and capabilities owned by the user)
Community Support	
1. Interest/enthusiasm shown by customer service to solve site visitors' problems	Two-way communication (Government websites should give users the opportunity to contact authorities, explain their views, or develop their own list of questions)
2. Quick response from customer service to questions from service users	-
3. Customer service knowledge to answer service user questions	-
4. The level of customer confidence in helping to solve problems faced	-

E-Government Policy Models in Handling Poverty Problems in The Hopeful Family Program (Case Study: Bandung Regency West.)

DISCUSSION

This study aims to describe the implementation of e-government with explains the quality of information on the West Bandung Regency Government website. The quality of information on e-government websites has an important role because it will have a broad impact on society. Information submitted by official government channels will be considered valid by the public, so that if the information submitted is incorrect it will result in reduced public trust in the government.

Based on the results of observations on website content, the implementation of e-government in West Bandung Regency can be categorized in the presence (informative) stage towards the interactive stage. As stated by Baum & Maio (2000), this stage indicates that the Bendung Barat website is still limited to providing static information, and has not provided space for the public to interact online with government elements.

This condition is indeed not much different from most local government websites which generally still function as informative or public relations media, and are not yet interactive media (Sosiawan, 2015). Although all websites except the Public Relations section already have links that function to contact relevant agencies via contact menu, but this feature is considered not optimal to accommodate interactive communication.

Meanwhile, from the perspective of information quality, the dimensions of accuracy, novelty, relevance and availability on the four websites have a fairly good rating. The deficiencies found are in the dimension of completeness of information, where on the main website, Dishubkominfo, and BPMP2T there are still links that lead to blank pages. On the website of the Public Relations Department, there are no menus that are standard for government agency website content, such as organizational structure, and job descriptions and agency functions. From the results of the interviews, information was obtained that there were indeed programs that had not yet been executed, so the menu had not been activated. For example the IP Camera menu on the Dishubkominfo website. This link should function to display traffic conditions at several points in the city of Bengkalis. However, because the camera installation has not been carried out, the result is that the feeding application to the camera has not been activated. Likewise the Management Information System (SIM) menu on the main website, because the system is still in the process of development (development). The difference in the quality of information from these four websites is possible because each website is managed by a different organization, which of course also differs in the maturity level of its management resources, starting from the amount of the management budget, e-government infrastructure, as well as the quality and quantity of the managing human resources.

In general, the quality of the information and website interface of the West Bendung Regency Government, which incidentally is a border area, can be assessed as quite good. Likewise, the availability of useful information for local communities, such as information on scholarships for native sons/daughters, information on permits, investment opportunities, and so on. This shows that there is good website management, as well as the will and political will of regional leaders to advance e-government in West Bandung. Besides that, the implementation of e-government is also supported by an adequate budget considering that West Bendung Regency is a region that generates local revenue. PAD) is the second largest,

A. Implementation of Local Government Policy on Basic Public Services in the Social Sector in Bandung Regency West.

Based on the results of interviews with informants related to the implementation of Regional Regulation No. 8 of 2009, it was found that the implementation of Bandung Regency West. City Government policies related to basic public services in the social sector in Bandung Regency West, began with socialization and testing of local regulations.

The socialization and trial of the regional regulation in question was carried out directly by the relevant agencies, namely the Bandung Regency West. Government Social Service and the Bandung Regency West. Government Parks and Cleaning Service as the leading sector. The target of the socialization is focused on the organizers and the community as potential service users. For this reason, socialization material delivered through the media and face-to-face is very much related to the rights and obligations of each party in the framework of implementing the regional regulation regarding basic public services in the social sector in Bandung Regency West..

Apart from outreach, it was found that prior to Perda No. 8 of 2009 was first implemented by testing the application of the regional regulation to the community, directly applied or implemented to grieving families with service officers (related officers) by visiting grieving families to explain the existence and implementation of the regional regulation regarding basic public services in the social sector in Bandung Regency West...

In terms of further implementation, the government of Bandung Regency West.. opens and provides the widest opportunity for the community, both through individuals and institutions, to take part in supporting the successful implementation of the Regional Regulation on basic public services in the social sector in Bandung Regency West.

In terms of further implementation, the government of Bandung Regency West opens and provides the widest opportunity for the community, both through individuals and institutions, to take part in supporting the successful implementation of the Regional Regulation on basic public services in the social sector in Bandung Regency West.

E-Government Policy Models in Handling Poverty Problems in The Hopeful Family Program (Case Study: Bandung Regency West.)

Another thing that was revealed in the interviews was that apart from receiving positive responses from residents who had used this service, each informant stated that they were still having problems implementing this regional regulation. Behind the perceived obstacles, the informant stated that he had taken anticipatory steps for the obstacles he felt.

Based on the data above, it appears that the reason for implementing Regional Regulation No. 8 of 2009 concerning basic public services in the social sector in Bandung Regency West has been in line with several expert opinions related to the definition of public policy itself, especially when it is associated with the conclusion of the formulation of a number of definitions. public policy which states that "public policy can be interpreted as things the government decides to do or do and things the government decides not to do or ignore".

Likewise the implementation of Regional Regulation No. 8 of 2009 concerning basic public services in the social field is associated with the conclusion which states that "public policy is a result of a more comprehensive, integrated and integrated and in-depth analysis of various alternative choices that will result in the best decision making on a problem".

Based on the two conclusions above, it appears that the steps taken by the City Government of Bandung Regency West, in this case the West Bandung district r, to implement the Perda are the right steps, bearing in mind that the policies taken by the government are decisions to take over some of the burden on its citizens as well as to overcome or minimize the problems faced by the community are related to the burden of grief. Related to the implementation steps of Regional Regulation No. 8 of 2008 by the West Bandung district r, appears to be in line or in accordance with several models in implementing public policies.

First, conformity with the George C Edward III Model. The intended suitability is seen through communication activities in the form of outreach, involvement of internal and external resources through collaborative program management, as well as strengthening the wishes and attitudes of managers, especially the Social Service and the Parks and Cleaning Service of the City of Bandung Regency West Government as leading sector and work partners in the successful implementation of Bandung Regency West government policies in terms of basic public services in the social sector in Bandung Regency West, and the bureaucratic structure, especially through inter-agency relations as the leading sector with each of its partners in the framework of implementing government policies in terms of basic public services social sector in Bandung Regency West.

Second, conformity with the Daniel Mazmanian and Paul A. Sabastier models. Conformity with the three variables classified by Daniel Mazmanian and Paul A. Sabastier is evident in the implementation of Regional Regulation no. 8 of 2009, especially when it is associated with independent variables with consideration of whether or not the problem is easily controlled over the implementation of the regional regulation. Likewise, when it comes to intervening with the situations and conditions that have occurred in the implementation of Regional Regulation No. 8 of 2009 with the government's ability to structure the implementation process and the government's ability to integrate the hierarchy among implementers, including in terms of recruiting implementing officials. Meanwhile, the suitability of the dependent variable can be seen in the steps taken by the government to provide understanding to all stakeholders in implementing the regional regulation.

Third, compatibility with the Merilee S Grindle model. According to this model, the success of implementing a policy is determined by the degree of implementability of a policy. For this reason, according to Merilee S Grindle, every policy must contain: (1) the interests affected by the policy, (2) the types of benefits to be generated, (3) the desired degree of change, (4) the position of the policy maker, (5) who implements it. program, as well as (5) the resources deployed. The suitability of the content meant by Merilee S Grindle appears implied and stated in the regional regulation.

In addition to conformity with several implementation models, the implementation of these regional regulations has experienced several obstacles or problems. The constraints referred to are each felt by the Bandung Regency West Government Parks and Cleanliness Service, the Bandung Regency West Government Social Service, and government partners in implementing Regional Regulation No. 8 of 2009, in this case the foundation for providing ambulances and WKSMB as corpse organizers in every sub-district within the Bandung Regency West.

Furthermore, the research results are directed to confirm the prerequisites for choosing the right model related to the implementation of a policy by the government. The prerequisites in question are considering the principle of "four right" from Nugroho (2006). The results of the confirmation show that the actions or steps taken by the government of Bandung Regency West in the context of implementing local government policies in the Social Sector Basic Public Services in Bandung Regency West are appropriate, except those related to target accuracy.

B. The Quality of Implementation of Basic Public Services in the Social Sector in Bandung Regency West

The results of this study indicate that the majority of respondents (61.5 percent) consider that the quality of basic public services in the social sector is in the good category. There were even 135 respondents or 35.8 percent who considered that the quality of basic public services in the social sector was very good. Meanwhile, only 10 people or 2.7 percent of respondents gave a bad assessment of the quality of basic public services in the social sector.

Different assessments differ from respondents, including bad ratings which are closely related to the opinion of Triguno (1997) which states that, "the best waiter, is to serve at any time, quickly and satisfactorily, to be polite, friendly and helpful, as well as

E-Government Policy Models in Handling Poverty Problems in The Hopeful Family Program (Case Study: Bandung Regency West.)

professional and capable" , thus services that do not show politeness, friendliness and indifference will describe a lack of empathy from a waiter.

Especially the majority of good and very good ratings compared to bad ratings, illustrating that the Free IASmo Program of the Bandung Regency West Government through basic public services in the social sector in the form of assistance with body equipment, transport of bodies (free ambulances), and funerals has been well received and felt by the people of the Bandung Regency West, even though a small portion of the service users say they are dissatisfied with giving a bad assessment of what they have received.

C. User Community Satisfaction with Basic Public Services in the Social Sector in Bandung Regency West Government

Regarding the satisfaction of the user community with basic public services in the social sector in Makassar, it shows that:

- a. The majority of respondents or 68.2 percent said they were satisfied with basic public services in the social sector. There even is 117 respondents or 31.0 percent said they were very satisfied with basic public services in the social sector. Meanwhile, only 3 respondents or 0.8 percent were dissatisfied with the basic public services in the social sector provided by the Bandung Regency West Government. The 3 respondents who were dissatisfied were all male, in other words there was not a single female respondent who was dissatisfied with basic public services.
- b. The largest proportion of respondents who are satisfied with basic public services in the social sector are aged ≤ 30 years, namely 72.9 percent. This proportion is almost the same as the respondents aged 41-50 years (71.2 percent). While the proportion of respondents aged over 50 years was 64.4 percent. while the proportion aged 31-40 is 63.9 percent. Meanwhile, the group of respondents who said they were very satisfied with public services were more aged > 50 years than those 31-40 years, namely 33.3 percent, as well as those aged ≤ 30 years and 41-50 years, each 27.1 percent. and 28.1 percent.
- c. The proportion of respondents who are dissatisfied with basic public services in the social sector tends to be more among those with junior high school education / Equivalent compared to those with high school education / equivalent which is only 1.0 percent. Meanwhile, none of the respondents with elementary/equivalent education and Academy/Higher Education were dissatisfied with basic public services in the social sector. On the other hand, more respondents who claimed to be satisfied with basic public services in the social sector had college/university education (78.3 percent) compared to those with high school/equivalent education (66.7 percent) as well as those with junior high school/equivalent and elementary/equivalent education respectively. 62.5 percent and 23.1 percent.

Meanwhile, respondents who said they were very satisfied tended to be more likely to have primary school education/equivalent education (76.9 percent) than those with junior high school/equivalent education (35.4 percent) as well as those with high school/equivalent education and academy/university education respectively (32.3 percent) and (21.7 percent).

The proportion of respondents who were dissatisfied with basic public services in the social sector tended to be more in the number of respondents who worked as Police / Military compared to those who were self-employed (1.1 percent). While those who work as civil servants and other types of work such as laborers and pedicab drivers, no one feels dissatisfied. Although dominant in the dissatisfied category, the proportion of respondents who work as Police /Military is greater in the satisfied category (84.2 percent) than respondents who work as civil servants or are self-employed and others, respectively 63.6 percent and 64.9 percent. Respondents who said they were very satisfied with basic public services in the social sector tended to be more among respondents who were self-employed and others (construction workers, pedicab drivers), namely 35.3 percent and 35.1 percent respectively. Followed by respondents who work as civil servants (25.4 percent) and Army/ Policy (10.5 percent).

The proportion of respondents who are dissatisfied with basic public services in the social sector tends to be more among respondents who earn Rp. 1,000,0001 – Rp. 2,000,000 and more than Rp. 3,000,000, respectively (2.0 percent) and (1.6 percent). While those who earn Rp. $\leq 1,000,000$ and Rp. 2,000,001 – Rp. 3,000,000 none of whom were dissatisfied. The proportion of respondents who are satisfied with basic public services in the social sector is more in proportion to respondents who have income above Rp. 3,000,000 compared to respondents who earn Rp. 2,000,000 – Rp. 3,000,000 (70.7 percent) and those who earn Rp. 1,000,0001 – Rp. 2,000,000 (65.7 percent) and earn Rp. $\leq 1,000,000$ (41.4 percent). Meanwhile, the proportion of respondents who are very satisfied with basic public services in the social sector is more in proportion to respondents who earn Rp. $\leq 1,000,000$ (58.6 percent) compared to respondents who earn Rp. 1,000,0001 – Rp. 2,000,000 (32.3 percent) and those who earn Rp. 2,000,001-3,000,000 and more than Rp. 3,000,000 respectively (29.3 percent) and (7.9 percent).

Analysis of the Influence of the Quality of Basic Public Services in the Social Sector on Community Satisfaction

The results of the analysis of the influence of the quality of the implementation of basic public services in the social sector partially show that there is an influence on the level of community satisfaction. However, when analyzed jointly on the level of community satisfaction, it shows that of the 5 indicators analyzed, two of them have a significant influence, namely reliability and empathy, while the other 3 indicators, namely physical evidence, responsiveness and ability of waiters, are supporters of service quality at the level of community satisfaction.

E-Government Policy Models in Handling Poverty Problems in The Hopeful Family Program (Case Study: Bandung Regency West.)

CONCLUSION

The results of this study conclude that in general the quality of information on the West Bandung Regency Government website is quite good. Weaknesses that can reduce the value of the quality of information exist in the dimensions of the completeness of the information, namely the existence of several links that lead to blank pages. The recommendation given from the results of this study is to increase improvement efforts so that all menus and links contained on the website can be completed with relevant information, so that users can obtain complete and accurate information.

This study describes empirical phenomena related to the quality of information using 5 (five) dimensions of measurement. For researchers who wish to continue this research, they can expand the area of study by measuring using a wider dimension of information quality.

Based on the results of data analysis, the results of this study are concluded as follows:

- a. The implementation of local government policies regarding basic public services in the social sector in Makassar City has been running in accordance with the public policy implementation model as confirmed by the four principles of right, namely (1) correctly answering problems, (2) implementing them correctly, (3) targeting them correctly, and (4) appropriate environment, in the selection of public policy implementation models.
- b. The quality of the implementation of basic public services in the social sector in Bandung Regency West Government as measured from the perspective of service users, namely the people of Bandung Regency West Government who have accessed and used basic public services in the social sector which include funeral services, funeral services (free ambulance), and funeral services indicate that the quality level was dominated by respondents who stated that they were of good quality, followed by respondents who stated that they were very qualified with very good ratings, then respondents who stated that they were not qualified with bad ratings.
- c. Satisfaction of the user community with basic public services in the social sector in Bandung Regency West Government as measured by the verbal response of respondents to respondents' satisfaction in receiving basic public services in the social sector which includes body kits, transport of bodies (free ambulances), and funerals are dominated by respondents who express satisfaction with high rating, followed by respondents who stated that they were very satisfied with a very high rating, then followed by respondents who stated that they were dissatisfied with a low rating.
- d. The results of the analysis of the influence of the quality of the implementation of basic public services the social sector partially shows the influence on the level of community satisfaction. However, when analyzed jointly on the level of community satisfaction, it shows that of the 5 indicators analyzed, two of them have a significant influence, namely reliability and empathy, while the other 3 indicators, namely physical evidence, responsiveness and ability of waiters, are supporters of service quality on satisfaction levels. public

REFERENCES

- 1) Arikunto, S. (2002). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- 2) Bambang, Sudaryana, 2016, *Metode Penelitian*, CV, Dedepublish Yogyakarta
- 3) -----, 2018, *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Konsep dan Teori*, CV, Dedepublish Yogyakarta
- 4) -----, 2021, *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Teori dan Aplikasi*, CV, Dedepublish Yogyakarta
- 5) BAPPENAS. (2015). *Laporan Akhir Koordinasi Strategis Kawasan Strategis Nasional (KSN)*,
- 6) *Perencanaan Program Kawasan Pengembangan Ekonomi Terpadu, Kawasan Perdagangan Bebas dan Pelabuhan Bebas, Kawasan Ekonomi Khusus, dan Kawasan Perbatasan*.
- 7) Bauer, C., & Scharl, A. (2000). Quantitive evaluation of Web site content and structure. *Internet Research*, 10(1), 31–44. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10662240010312138>
- 8) Baum, C., & Maio, A. D. (2000). *Gartner's Four Phases of EGovernment Model*. Stamford: GartnerGroup Inc.
- 9) Convelo, Cevilla G., (dkk), 1993, *Pengantar Metode Penelitian*, UI, Jakarta
- 10) DeLone, W. H., & McLean, E. R. (1992). Information systems success: the quest for the dependent variable. *Information System Research*, 3(1), 60–95.
- 11) Direktorat Jenderal Aplikasi Informatika Kementerian Komunikasi dan Informasi, 2015, *Rencana Strategis Direktorat Jenderal Aplikasi Informatika t.a. 2015 – 2019*. Kemenkominfo, Jakarta.
- 12) Garcia, A. C. B., Maciel, C., & Pinto, F. B. (2005, August). A quality inspection method to evaluate e-government sites. In *International Conference on Electronic Government* (pp. 198-209). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- 13) Halaris, C., Magoutas, B., Papadomichelaki, X., & Mentzas, G. (2007). Classification and synthesis of quality approaches in e-government services. *Internet research*, 17(4), 378-401.
- 14) Holle, E. S. (2011). *Pelayanan Publik Melalui Electronic Government; Upaya Meminimalisir Praktek Maladministrasi Dalam Meningkatkan Public Service*. *Jurnal Sasi*, 17(3).
- 15) Henriksson, A., Yi, Y., Frost, B., & Middleton, M. (2006). *Evaluation instruments for e-government websites*.

E-Government Policy Models in Handling Poverty Problems in The Hopeful Family Program (Case Study: Bandung Regency West.)

Electronic Government An International Journal, 4(2), 204–226.

- 16) Jogiyanto, H. M. (1990). Analisis dan Disain Sistem Informasi. Yogyakarta: Andi.
- 17) KEMKOMINFO. (2016). Buku Putih Komunikasi dan Informatika 2016. Jakarta.
- 18) Knight, S., & Burn, J. (2005). Developing a Framework for Assessing Information Quality on the WorldWide Web Introduction – The Big Picture What Is Information Quality? *Informing Science Journal*, 8.
- 19) Masyhur, F. (2014). Kinerja Website Resmi Pemerintah Provinsi di Indonesia. *Jurnal Pekommas*, 17(1),9–14.
- 20) Mardalis, 1999, Metode Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Proposal. Bumi Aksara, Jakarta
- 21) Napitupulu, D. B. (2017). Pengujian kerangka kerja pemeringkatan e-government di Indonesia(PeGI): Studi kasus di tingkat kementerian. *Jurnal Penelitian Komunikasi*, 20, 15-30.
- 22) O'Brien, J. A. (2005). Pengantar Sistem Informasi. Jakarta: Penerbit Salemba Empat.
- 23) Panopoulou, E., Tambouris, E., & Tarabanis, K. (2008). A framework for evaluating web sites of public authorities. *Aslib Proceedings*, 60(5), 517–546. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00012530810908229>
- 24) Papadomichelaki, X., & Mentzas, G. (2012). e-GovQual: A multiple-item scale for assessing e-government service quality. *Government information quarterly*, 29(1), 98-109.
- 25) Rieh, S. Y. (2002). Judgment of information quality and cognitive authority in the Web. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 53(2), 145–161. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.10017>
- 26) Saha, P., Nath, A. K., & Salehi-Sangari, E. (2012). Evaluation of government e-tax websites : an information quality and system quality approach. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 6(3), 300–321. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17506161211251281>
- 27) Shankar, G., & Watts, S. (2003). A relevant, believable approach for data quality assessment. In *Proceedings of 8th International Conference on Information Quality* (pp. 178–189).
- 28) Sitokdana, M. N. N. (2015). Evaluasi Implementasi eGovernment Pada Situs Web Pemerintah Kota Surabaya, Medan, Banjarmasin, Makassar dan Jayapura. *Jurnal Buana Informatika*, 6(4), 289–300.
- 29) Sosiawan, E. A. (2015). Evaluasi Implementasi E-Government pada Situs Web Pemerintah Daerah di Indonesia: Perspektif Content dan Manajemen. In *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Informatika* (pp. 88–98).
- 30) Sugiyono. (2008). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif dan R&D. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 31) Sosiawan, E. A. (2015, June). Evaluasi implementasi e-government pada situs web pemerintah daerah di Indonesia: Prespektif content dan manajemen. In *Seminar Nasional Informatika (SEMNASIF)* (Vol. 1, No. 5).
- 32) Tambouris, Efthimios, Gorilas, Stelios and Boukis, George, 2001, Investigation of Electronic Government, Available in : www.eurociti.org.br/12/02/2005 , diakses tanggal 20 November 2019.
- 33) Tate, M., Evermann, J., Hope, B., & Barnes, S. (2007, January). Perceived service quality in a university web portal: revising the e-equal instrument. In *2007 40th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS'07)* (pp. 147b-147b). IEEE.
- 34) Wang, R. W., & Strong, D. M. (1996). Beyond Accuracy: What Data Quality Means to Data Consumers. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 12, 5. <https://doi.org/10.2307/40398176>
- 35) Wiratmo, L. B., Irfan, N., & Kuwatono. (2017). Website Pemerintah Daerah sebagai Sarana Online Public Relations. *Jurnal ASPIKOM*, 3(2), 326–339.
- 36) Yunita, N. P., & Aprianto, R. D. (2018). Kondisi Terkini Perkembangan Pelaksanaan E- Government di Indonesia: Analisis Website. In *Seminar Nasional Teknologi Informasi dan Komunikasi* (pp. 23-24).
- 37) Zeithaml, V. A., Parasuraman, A., & Malhorta, A. (2002). Service quality delivery through web sites: A critical review of extant knowledge. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 30, 362–375.